

EUNIVERSAL'S SMART GRID SOLUTIONS FOR THE COORDINATED OPERATION & PLANNING OF MV AND LV NETWORKS WITH HIGH EV INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT

EUniversal project aims to facilitate the use of flexibility services and interlink distribution system's active management with electricity markets. Implementing market-based flexibility services implies a change in distribution network monitoring and control towards a more predictive approach. However, integrating cost-effective monitoring and control tools for the LV network is still quite challenging. Within the project, a set of operation and planning tools have been developed for a coordinated quantification and activation of flexibility in HV, MV and LV distribution networks. The paper presents the tools developed for the Portuguese pilot and shows preliminary results obtained when considering network operation scenarios characterized by large scale integration of DER and EV.

INTRODUCTION

Taking advantage of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) flexibility for improving distribution network efficiency, reliability and resilience is widely recognized by DSOs. Congestion Management (CM) and Voltage Control (VC) are considered the most relevant system needs, considering the expected technical impacts of growing integration of DER and Electric Vehicles (EV).

While current Advanced Distribution Management Systems (ADMS) are moving towards a predictive management strategy, LV network management still require the development an adequate framework, considering their reduced monitoring capabilities and the high error of LV load and generation forecasts.

Similarly, current network planning methodologies follow a business-as-usual model considering conventional network reinforcement investments, therefore requiring new approaches to assess the benefit of long-term flexibility products [1].

This paper describes the smart grid tools developed in EUniversal project for enabling DSO procurement of market-based flexibility long and short-term services. The main objectives of the tools are:

- Enable market-driven flexibility services for distribution networks [1]
- Promote a coordinated management of flexibility between HV, MV and LV distribution networks

- Enhance the observability and control of LV distribution network through a data-driven approach, minimizing investment in additional monitoring.
- Develop novel distribution network planning methodologies to assess the long-term impact of flexibility and market-based services, integrating resilience as new criterion.

EUNIVERSAL ARCHITECTURE

Figure 1. EUniversal reference architecture

The EUniversal project aims to develop a universal approach for the use of flexibility by DSOs and their interaction with the new flexibility markets, enabled through the development of the Universal Market Enabling Interface (UMEI).

As shown in Fig. 1, the UMEI connects the DSO systems to the external market platforms and flexibility aggregators by using an agnostic, adaptable, modular and evolutionary approach. The integration of two Flexibility Market Platforms is being tested: NODES and N-SIDE market platforms with distinct clearing methodologies. While NODES is based on a pay-as-bid pricing mechanism, N-SIDE is based on a pool system with a pay-as-clear pricing mechanism. In addition, in the case of NODES platform the DSO selects the flexibility bids, while in the case of N-SIDE, the selection of the FSP bids is done by the market platform. In the later case, it means that the clearing does

not use detailed grid information. Therefore, to allow an efficient flexibility bids selection without grid topology awareness, the dynamic flexibility areas concept is proposed, as explained below.

MULTI-LEVEL PREVENTIVE MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

EUniversal project is developing a multi-level preventive management framework for enabling DSO procurement of day-ahead market-based flexibility services for CM and VC. The main characteristics are summarized below:

- Capability to forecast the network status and to identify a priori potential MV and LV network constraints (voltage violations and congestions). The main innovations concern LV networks, where data-driven tools such as the LV state estimation algorithm is proposed to overcome limited monitoring and network characterization.
- Multi-level approach for the assessment of flexibility needs, considering the participation of LV flexibility to help solving constraints in MV networks.
- Enablement of the selection and validation of flexibility bids also considering the impact of flexibility mobilization in both LV and MV network.
- Compatible with different market designs, both continuous or auction based, with day-ahead and/or intraday activity.

The next sections describe the different tools developed within the project.

MV and LV network state and constraint forecasting

The main objective is forecasting the network status for the next day/hours, identifying potential voltage and congestion violations, based on load and generation forecasting tools. MV state forecasting will be performed by a multi-period power flow tool from GridOS® [2] and more specifically of its Integrated Distribution Planning module (IDP [3]).

For the LV network status, model-based power tools might not be able to run considering the typical poor characterization of LV networks topology and feeder electric characteristics. On the other hand, smart metering data have the potential to improve the observability of LV networks, considering the load and voltage magnitude measurements. However, communication infrastructure limitations do not allow to collect data in real-time, requiring the adoption of tools that can extract knowledge from historical data. Therefore, a LV state estimation tool is being deployed in EUniversal for forecasting and real-time monitoring of LV networks using smart metering historical data.

LV state estimation

The Data-driven State Estimator (DdSE) is a tool designed to provide the most likely state of the system (voltage magnitudes and/or active power injections) by reconstructing the missing information from an incomplete state. The basic principle is to search for analog events in the historical data, using a set of explanatory variables, to extrapolate a future operating scenario [4]. Without resorting to any topological or electrical characterization of the grid, it relies exclusively on historical data, along with some exogenous information such as weather

forecasts, calendar variables, and market signals, in case they help to explain the voltage and active power patterns. Figure 2 illustrates the use of the DdSE in a real time application.

Figure 2. Current voltage magnitude estimation (e.g., every 15.min) using the analogue search method.

MV-LV coordinated identification of flexibility needs

Ensuring coordinated mobilization of flexible resources between MV and LV networks is crucial to avoid causing further problems and maximize the use of the available flexibility. The iterative procedure represented in Figure 3 is adopted for enabling LV flexible resources to help solving technical constraints in the MV network, while ensuring that no further technical problems result from flexibility provision. It consists of the following steps:

- 1) If restrictions are detected at the MV level, the MV multi-period OPF is used to compute the operation plan for the DSO assets.
- 2) If technical constraints remain, then the MV Flexibility Scheduling tool is used to compute the flexibility needs for the MV network.
- 3) The Data-driven Voltage Control (DdVC) uses the expected voltage in the MV/LV substation to determine:
 - a) The additional flexibility required to solve LV voltage constraints remaining at the LV networks
 - b) The security limits for the aggregated flexibility at the MV/LV substation
- 4) The flexibility needs are sent to the market platform through the UMEI.

MV multi-period OPF

At MV level, it is assumed that the modelling of the distribution network is known, including an half-hourly update of the switches, transformer taps and capacitor banks position. The forecasts of the MV loads and generation, as well as the computed power flows at MV/LV substations are also provided. The DSO uses the multi-period OPF to compute the optimal network topology and set points for its own assets, i.e., its capacitor banks and voltage regulator (or transformer taps).

Dynamic flexibility areas definition

If necessary, additional flexibility is mobilized from the MV and LV resources through local flexibility markets. The concept of dynamic flexibility areas is proposed in EUniversal to increase the liquidity of the local flexibility market and to allow zonal flexibility aggregation for portfolio management, while considering, in a simplified way, the local characteristics of the technical restrictions of the distribution network.

The MV Flexibility Scheduling tool and the Data-driven

Voltage Control (DdVC) described below identify those nodes that can solve the technical constraint(s) and group them into zones according to their impact on the technical constraints to be solved, or on other potential technical constraints that could occur. For each of the LV and MV zones identified, the amount of flexibility needed to solve the identified technical constraints is computed and shared with the flexibility market platform to provide relevant but simplified technical information to support the economical clearing.

Figure 3. Implementation of MV-LV coordinated flexibility needs identification.

MV flexibility scheduling

The MV Flexibility Scheduling tool is run for the activation of flexibility in the MV grid. It is based on the dynamic computation of zonal flexibility needs that would solve the forecasted constraints. Zonal flexibility needs allow aggregators to manage portfolios with their zonal resources, and to simplify the needs of complex market clearing algorithms based on grid topologies to select the optimal flexibility bids to solve the constraints.

The computation of the zonal flexibility needs is based on three main steps, as shown in Figure 4:

1. Computation of two types of sensitivities indices [5]:
 - a. Buses voltages variation when there is a unitary increment of active power in a bus
 - b. Lines currents variation when there is a unitary increment of active power in a bus
2. Segmentation: the grid buses are grouped into clusters. The clustering process is based on a distance function $d(i, j)$ that considers that two buses i and j are close when the activation of the same flexibility on them has a similar impact (assessed by the

sensitivity indices) on the problematic grid elements. Problematic grid elements are those grid elements that are close to or beyond their constraint limits (maximum and minimum voltages for buses, maximum current for lines). Only problematic grid elements are considered, which is achieved with a weighting function W_m that multiplies the sensitivities difference of the distance function, as shown in the step 2 of Figure 4.

Figure 4. MV zonal flexibility needs computation

3. Computation of the zonal flexibility needs: the flexibility needs that would solve the forecasted grid constraints are computed through an optimization problem for the individual zones and for combination of them. Providing flexibility needs by tuples of zones help a) in case individual zones cannot solve the constraints (e.g. when solving the existing constraints would generate other additional constraints), and b) to provide more selection alternatives to the market platform for a more cost-effective flexibility bids selection and liquidity.

Data-driven Voltage Control (DdVC)

The Data-driven Voltage Control (DdVC) is a tool that exploits the linearized dependencies between voltage magnitudes and active power injections within a LV grid to allow solving voltage violations without resorting to the grid's topology nor to its electrical parameters. Also, it allows to find the maximum admissible ranges of flexibility a customer can provide that ensures the non-violation of voltage magnitude limits.

As explained before, the core concept behind the DdVC is also the calculation of sensitivity factors ($S_{Vi,j}$) as in the MV flexibility scheduling tool. However, in this case only voltage constraints are considered. These relationships can be estimated via multi-linear regression using historical data gathered from smart meters, while considering data privacy constraints [6].

The DdVC expects to receive regular updates of historical data (e.g., every 24h or 48h) as illustrated in Figure 5 (input 1) so it adapts the sensitivity factors to the time-varying consumption patterns, also using a sliding window to “forget” old behaviors. From this calculation, the tool

offers several functionalities, namely:

Solve voltage violations: the current or a forecast system state (input 2), which can be built by the DdSE described above, is evaluated considering the constraints (input 3) and in case of voltage violations an optimization is run to find the necessary amount to flexibility to solve them (output 5).

Flexibility ranges: using the current or a forecasted system state (input 2) and the constraints (input 3), the tool determines the range of flexibility that can be provided by each customer (output 6) and the admissible power exchange at the MV/LV substation (output 7) that ensures the non-violation of voltage constraints.

Check new system state: again, from a system state (input 3), considering the constraints (input 3), and providing the flexibility that will be activated (input 4), the DSO can obtain the new system state (output 8), for example to validate the market clearing.

Figure 5: Inputs and output of the DdVC

Revisiting the concept of dynamic zone introduced before, the DdVC exploits the calculated sensitivity factors to create flexibility perimeters, i.e., aggregation of customers whose consumption and generation cause similar effects on the voltage measured at a certain point in the grid. As illustrated in Figure 6, the algorithm identifies the flexibility zones for a single LV feeder, with respect to the customer located at node 5. Please note that the topology is unknown to the tool, but it is naturally expected that closer customers will be able to contribute almost similarly to solve a potential violation, hence the perimeter around node 5. If there is not enough flexibility within this perimeter (or if it is expensive), other perimeters, although physically more distant (lower sensitivity factor), can contribute to the solution of the violation.

For each LV perimeters (see Figure 6), the amount of flexibility needed per perimeter to solve the identified technical constraints is computed, as in Figure 7.

Flexibility bid selection and validation

Depending on the flexibility market design, flexibility bids selection may be conducted by the DSO or by the market platform. In both cases, the selection of the bids will aim to minimize the operation costs, ensuring that the existing constraints are solved and that no additional technical constraints are created.

Final validation can also be requested to the DSO after the market clearing, to ensure that no additional technical restriction is created.

Both flexibility bid selection by the DSO (in the case of NODES Platform) and validation will be performed considering the sensitivity coefficients calculated by MV

scheduling and DdVC tools described. This will be ensured by collecting the viable flexibility. This approach presents an effective alternative to conventional OPF algorithms, since the optimization problem remains linear.

Figure 6: Flexibility perimeters when a voltage violation is detected in node 5.

Figure 7: Required flexibility per perimeter.

DISTRIBUTION RESILIENCE NETWORK PLANNING WITH FLEXIBLE RESOURCES

While EV and other DER can impose technical challenges to distribution network operation, they also offer valuable flexibility for the operation of the system at times of technical constraints or even severe disturbances. A novel resilience-oriented planning tool is developed, revisiting and expanding conventional, reliability-informed planning methodologies to incorporate flexibility as an attractive alternative to costly network reinforcement, and also explicitly considering and assessing the resilience of the network against extreme events, such as windstorms, floods and wildfires. A diverse portfolio of emerging smart and flexible solutions are considered for assessing and enhancing distribution network resilience, namely: energy storage, EV and microgrids providing self-healing capabilities.

Methodology description

The main objective of the planning exercise consists of integrating resilience as a new metric in distribution network planning and decision-making. Accordingly, the effect of resilience network enhancement solutions is assessed not only in terms of cost and network losses, but also using risk metrics (e.g., VaR, CVaR, END, etc.) which are capable of quantifying “tail” risks (i.e., high-impact, low-probability events) and bespoke time-dependent resilience metrics (e.g., FLEP [6]), capable of reflecting the behavior of the system before, during, and after extreme events. The outcome is portfolios of resilience enhancement solutions which would optimize pre-selected risk and resilience metrics. These resilience enhancement portfolios in the perspective of the decision maker are defined based on four-step methodology, as

follows:

- a) **Options definition:** this step consists of establishing and characterizing a set of investment alternatives in terms of energy and capacity for the network under study. Local and mobile storage devices, intelligent automation enabling islanded operation, demand-side response, and traditional reinforcement solutions are examples of options to be studied. Note that an expansion plan can consist of a unique or a combination of multiple options.
- b) **Random Scenario Generation:** an event simulator is the main tool for this step. Apart from typical operational scenarios, which are used to evaluate traditional risk metrics (e.g. CVAR, END), this tool allows to generate random spatial and temporal evolutions of extreme weather events (e.g. storms). This is especially important to quantify, in a stochastic manner under uncertainty, how the different sections of the network are impacted by the event and the underlying time- and event-dependent fragility of the exposed assets.
- c) **Resilience Metrics Quantification:** the quantification of the benefits of the expansion plan (from Step (a)) is performed in this step by deploying and quantifying a wide set of risk and resilience metrics. Accordingly, simple tools, like load flow and reliability assessment, and more advanced like AC cascading failure models for resilience applications [7] and multi-temporal OPF [8] are going to be used.
- d) **Multi-criteria evaluation and decision-making:** once all expansion plans are evaluated and ranked, then a multi-criteria decision process is set based on the preferences of the decision maker for achieving efficient trade-offs between the desired planning criteria (e.g., cost, reliability and resilience).

It is worth remarking that expansion plans can be optimized to include the best set of options if the multi-criteria assessment fails to identify a plan with minimum performance requirements.

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CONCLUSIONS

EUniversal aims at facilitating the integration of flexibility in distribution networks. The Universal Market Enabling Interface (UMEI) will be implemented to facilitate the implementation of market-oriented flexibility services in an agnostic, adaptable and cost-effective way.

This paper describes the smart grid tools developed the project for enabling DSO procurement of market-based flexibility service, namely to provide support to congestion

management and voltage control in MV and LV networks characterized by large scale integration of DER and EV. A multi-level preventive management framework was presented, combining enhanced conventional ADMS tools with innovative data-driven algorithms taking advantage of historical data from smart meters. The coordinated operation of both, enables the deployment of a novel dynamic flexibility area definition as well as coordinated mobilization of flexibility between MV and LV networks. For long-term services conventional planning methodologies have been adapted to integrate flexibility as a network asset for postponing investment and improving network resilience.

The tool presented are being deployed and tested in the Portuguese pilot, integrating both MV and LV flexibility resources. Results are expected to contribute to assessment of distinct market clearing mechanisms and flexibility aggregation strategies.

REFERENCES

- [1] EUniversal project, "Deliverable 2.1. - Grid flexibility services definition", February 2021. https://euniversal.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/EUniversal_D2.1.pdf
- [2] GridOS – <https://www.opusonesolutions.com/gridos-platform/>
- [3] IDP - <https://www.opusonesolutions.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Product-Overview-IDP-Digital.pdf>
- [4] R. J. Bessa, G. Sampaio, J. Pereira, and V. Miranda, "Probabilistic low voltage state estimation using analog-search techniques," in 20th Power Sys. Comp. Conf. (PSCC 2018), Dublin, Ireland, Jun. 2018.
- [5] G. Sampaio, R. J. Bessa, C. Gonçalves, C. Gouveia, "Conditional parametric model for sensitivity factors in LV grids: A privacy-preserving approach," in 22nd Power Sys. Comp. Conf. (PSCC 2022), Porto, Portugal, Jun. 2022.
- [6] K. Christakou, J.-Y. LeBoudec, M. Paolone, and D.-C. Tomozei, "Efficient Computation of Sensitivity Coefficients of Node Voltages and Line Currents in Unbalanced Radial Electrical Distribution Networks," IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON SMART GRID, vol. 4, no. 2, Jun. 2013.
- [7] M. Panteli, P. Mancarella, D. N. Trakas, E. Kyriakides and N. D. Hatziargyriou, "Metrics and Quantification of Operational and Infrastructure Resilience in Power Systems," in IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 4732-4742, Nov. 2017.
- [8] M. Noebels, R. Preece and M. Panteli, "AC Cascading Failure Model for Resilience Analysis in Power Networks," IEEE Systems Journal.
- [9] H. M. Costa, J. Sumaili, A. G. Madureira and C. Gouveia, "A multi-temporal optimal power flow for managing storage and demand flexibility in LV networks," 2017 IEEE Manchester PowerTech, 2017, pp. 1-6.